

BIOPLASTICS AND GREEN COMPOSITES FROM RENEWABLE RESOURCES: WHERE WE ARE AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS!

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Introduction

The sky rocketing price of petroleum along with its dwindling nature coupled with climate change concern and continued population growth have drawn the urgency for the plastic industries in adapting towards sustainability. The government's push for green products, consumers' desire and energy conservation are some of the key factors that drive research towards the development of renewable resource-based polymeric biomaterials. The use of bio- or renewable carbon unlike petro-carbon for manufacturing bioplastics and biobased materials is moving forward for a reduced carbon footprint. The goal is to use biobased materials containing the maximum possible amount of renewable biomass-based derivatives to have a sustainable future. Search for potential biobased alternatives from energy to plastics and their viability for real world uses is directed towards our reduced dependency on petroleum [1].

The incorporation of bio-resources, e.g. crop-derived green plastics and plant derived natural fibres into composite structures are gaining prime importance in designing and engineering of green composites. Biocomposites derived from natural fibers and conventional petro-based thermoplastic and thermoset plastics have been developed for automotive parts, building structures and consumer products uses. Renewable resource based bioplastics like polylactic acid (PLA), polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), biobased polytrimethylene terephthalate (PTT), cellulosic plastics, soy/corn/wheat protein based bioplastics and vegetable oils derived

bioresins need value-added and diverse applications to compete with the fossil fuel derived plastics.

Through reactive blends, biobased materials are under constant development in the form of composites and nanocomposites. Natural fibres are lighter, less expensive, have superior specific strength, require comparatively less energy to produce, are good for the environment, biodegradable and have superior sound abatement characteristics as compared to glass fibres. All of these attributes are quite favorable, especially in the automotive sector where even a fractional weight saving can make a significant contribution to energy savings with reduced gasoline consumption and with added advantages of eco-friendliness. It is true that natural fibres are comparatively hydrophilic and less thermally stable as compared to glass fibers.

However, the recent developments of natural fibre technologies overcome these disadvantages if used intelligently. Hybrid and intelligently engineered green composites are going to be the major drivers for sustainable developments. Besides agricultural natural fibers like flax, industrial hemp, kenaf, jute, sisal and henequen; inexpensive biomasses such as wheat straw, rice stalks, corn stovers, grasses, soy stalks and lignin (the byproducts from pulp and paper and lingo-cellulosic ethanol industries) have great potential for use in sustainable biobased composite materials. Natural fibre reinforcements in conjunction with nanotechnology are poised to create major breakthroughs. Chemistry plays a vital role and thus possesses several opportunities and challenges like effective chemical modification of reinforcements, use of novel coupling agents, and

matrix modifications. This paper discusses the current status, opportunities and challenges of bioplastics, natural fibre composites and all green composites in structural and semi-structural applications.

Bioplastics- Major Drivers and Trends

Bioplastics are referred to as materials that are either biodegradable, derived from both renewable and non-renewable resources, or materials that are non-biodegradable and derived from renewable resources. Blending of different bioplastics can also be done to achieve a bioplastic blend with optimum properties designed for specific requirements. A broad classification of bioplastics is shown schematically in Fig. 1. The global bioplastics growth is around

microorganisms in to carbon dioxide, methane, inorganic compounds, or biomass in a specified period of time. In other way biodegradable polymers are also those, which can undergo microbial induced chain scission leading to mineralization, which also include photodegradation, oxidation and hydrolysis. This can alter the polymer structure during the degradation process.

Initially when bioplastics entered into focus, there was more interest in developing biodegradable plastics. Currently, we look more towards biobased plastics although biodegradable plastics still are progressing in the market place. The factors guiding biodegradable type bioplastics growth is the market’s need for plastics that are biodegradable, to solve formidable problem of disposing plastic waste and limited landfill capacities. The idea of biobased

BIOPLASTICS: A BROAD CLASSIFICATION

Fig. 1: A broad Classification of Bioplastics

30% as contrast to 5% growth rate of petroleum-based plastics. A recent report suggests that up to 90% of all polymers can be made technically from bio-resources [2].

The bioplastics as discussed here may or may not be biodegradable (compostable). Biodegradable polymers are capable of undergoing decomposition, primarily through enzymatic action of

plastics is to achieve as much bio-based content in the plastic formulations while maintaining the required performance at an affordable cost. The use of bioplastics is aimed to reduce carbon footprint and to offer a broad range of functionalities optimized for different type of applications.

Biobased and also Biodegradable type bioplastics from Renewable Resources: The well-known renewable resources that are capable of making biodegradable plastics are starch and cellulose. However both starch and cellulose are not plastic in the native form but can be converted to plastics thorough innovative fermentation and/or through polymer technology. The most emerging renewable resource-based bioplastics (**Scheme 1**) are polylactides (PLA) and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs). Under PHA family of bioplastics, again the two important plastics are polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate (PHBV) and polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB).

Polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate (PHBV)

Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) Polylactide (PLA)

Scheme 1: *Emerging Renewable Resource-based Bioplastics*

Poly lactide or polylactic acid (PLA) is a highly versatile biodegradable polymer that has been derived from renewable resources like corn. The hydrolysis of cornstarch yields sugars that can be fermented to lactic acid followed by polymerization in yielding polylactic acid. PLA is now produced commercially in different parts of world. NatureWorks LLC in USA is the lead producer of PLA now globally. Some other companies are Teijin in Japan, HISUN in China, PURAC in Netherland and Inventa Fischer in Germany etc. [2, 3]. The current production of PLA globally is around 300 million pounds per year and its predicted growth is more than 2 billion pounds per year in a very near future.

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are known as bacterial bioplastics. These bioplastics have shown a lot of promise as novel materials due to their renewability, biodegradability and biocompatibility [4]. Poly (3-hydroxy butyrate) (PHB) and poly (3-

hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) are the main representatives of the polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs). PHBV is a copolymer consisting of randomly arranged hydroxybutyrate (HB) and hydroxyvalerate (HV) units. PHB and PHBV are the waterproof biopolymer obtained from renewable resources. Unlike other biopolymer like PLA its heat deflection temperature is around 100 C as contrast to around 55 C for PLA. Again PHA bioplastics do have small tendency to creep. Thus researchers are looking in developing PHA-based biomaterials for durable applications. Telles, a joint venture between Metabolix and ADM in USA is commercializing PHA bioplastics. Telles has a 50,000 ton capacity for PHA production. A varieties companies in China major being Tianan Biologic and Tianjin Green Bioscience (joint venture with DSM) are commercializing/developing commercialization for PHA production in large scale. Currently the PHA production globally is around 130 million per year with a predicted growth to more than 1 billion pound per year in a couple of years [3].

Biobased but not biodegradable type of bioplastics: This class of bioplastic has attracted a good deal of attention recently. These recent biobased plastics are polyolefins e.g. renewably sourced bio-polyethylene and bio-polypropylene and biobased nylons [1]. The base for bio-polyolefins (bio-PE and bio-PP) is bioethanol. The corn and sugar cane have been used predominantly in producing ethanol in USA and Brazil respectively. The dehydration of ethanol (C₂H₅OH) can produce ethylene (C₂H₄), which on subsequent purification and polymerization produces polyethylene. The largest bio-PE production from ethanol has been started in September 2010 by Braskem in Brazil with an annual production capacity of 200,000 tonnes. Braskem also plans to mass produce bio-ethanol derived bio-polypropylene, although the company has not yet revealed the process in making these.

Bionylons are also moving towards market place and the major manufacturers include DuPont, Arkema, DSM and BASF. DuPont's Zytel® RS nylon 10/10 contains 100 percent renewably sourced content while nylon 6/10 contains 63 percent. Rilsan® 11 is Elf Aquitaine's (part of Arkema) brand name for its

bionylon which has good mechanical property combined with chemical resistance. It can be widely used for automotive applications such as fuel line tubing [5].

The bioplastics market is on a strong growth pace and most of the growth is expected to come from renewable-based polyolefin substitutes, as opposed to compostables [6]. Bioplastics cover approximately 10-15% of the total plastics market and will increase its market share to 25-30% by 2020 [7]. Many companies are showing interest in entering and investing in this market. More than 5000 bioplastics processing companies are expected by 2020 with over 500 already available [7].

Natural Fiber Composites- Key Insights

The usage of natural fibre as reinforcement for composites application is receiving increased attention. Natural fibres are lighter, less expensive, have superior specific strength, require comparatively less energy to produce, good for the environment, biodegradable and have superior sound abatement characteristics as compared to glass fibres. Natural fibers combined with traditional plastics offer good performance at lower prices creating huge potential to replace competing materials in automotive applications where even a fractional weight saving can make a significant contribution to energy savings with reduced gasoline consumption and with added advantages of eco-friendliness. Natural fiber production has lower environmental impact compared to traditional synthetic fiber production.

The light-weight natural fibre composites can help in improved fuel efficiency and reduced emission in the use phase of the component especially in automotive applications. As well, end of life incineration of natural fibres results in recovery of energy and carbon credits.

Automotive, construction, packaging and consumer products are the major segment for natural fiber composite applications. Bast fibers such as flax, kenaf, jute, hemp, etc. and leaf fibres like sisal and henequen are the well known fibers in natural fiber composite uses. Recently, agricultural residues like wheat straw, soy stalk and perennial grasses like

switch grass and miscathus have received a good deal of attention in developing biocomposites and green composites for automotive and consumer product applications. Demand for natural fiber composites are growing mainly because of their increased acceptability, awareness and also due to consumer pull towards greener products.

Many natural fibres have been investigated for composites applications including flax, hemp, jute straw, wood, rice husk, wheat, barley, oats, cane (sugar and bamboo), grass, reeds, kenaf, ramie, oil palm empty fruit bunch, sisal, coir, water, kapok, banana fibre, and pineapple leaf fibre [8].

All Green Composites

Development of all green composites by combining bioplastics derived from renewable resources and natural fibers has greatly attracted researchers in recent years. The most important feature of green composites is their complete biodegradability although all green composites made from biofibre and renewable resource-based non-biodegradable plastic are not biodegradable. In the later type of all green composites the most attractive attribute is their long-term durability and reduced carbon footprint. A study on the fabrication of green composites was initially reported by Herrmann et al. [9]. The research on all green composites from renewable resource-based bioplastics and natural fibres are extensively studied [10-13].

Concluding Remarks

It is apparent that choice of material and design has great impact on society and environment. Sustainable society's need of the hour is environmentally safe materials and processing methods. Life cycle assessment is of paramount importance now at every stage of a product's life, right from initial synthesis to final disposal. Use of agricultural fibres in composites is seen mainly as an opportunity for profitable market but it is to be understood that economic arguments alone will not cause this technology to take off. Performance improvement in natural fiber composites and green

composites is needed to cater more applications by industries.

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